

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

医中誌 Web

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健常成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** 健常成人
- I** SGS を含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 "sulforaphane glucosinolate"/TA or スルフォラファングルコシノレート/TA [2 件]

#2 Sulphoraphane/TH [275 件]
#3 "Sulphoraphane"/TA or "Sulforafan"/TA or スルフォラファン/TA or スルフォラフェン/TA or "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane"/TA or "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate"/TA or "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or "Methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA [149 件]
#4 #1 or #2 or #3 [289 件]
#5 "Glucosinolates"/TH [47 件]
#6 "Glucosinolates"/TA or グルコシノレート/TA [16 件]
#7 #5 or #6 [55 件]
#8 "Isothiocyanates"/TH [1,627 件]
#9 "Isothiocyanates"/TA or イソチオシアネート/TA or イソチアシアン酸類/TA or イソチオシアナート/TA [372 件]
#10 #8 or #9 [1,776 件]
#11 #7 or #10 [1,818 件]
#12 #4 and #11 [258 件]
#13 ブロッコリスプラウト/TA or "BS 抽出物"/TA [4 件]
#14 "SFN"/TA and "SGS"/TA [2 件]
#15 #12 or #13 or #14 [261 件]
#16 (#15) and (PT=会議録除く) [97 件]
#17 (CK=動物) not (CK=ヒト) [915,864 件]
#18 #16 not #17 [76 件]

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2023/08/15

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

#3 "Sulphoraphane"/TA or "Sulforaphan"/TA or スルフォラファン/TA or スルフォラフェン/TA or "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane"/TA or "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate"/TA or "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or "Methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA [149 件]

→【案（黄色箇所）】"Sulphoraphane"/TA or "Sulforaphan"/TA or スルフォラファン/TA or スルフォラフェン/TA or "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane"/TA or "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate"/TA or "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or "Methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or SFN/TA or 実生/MTH or Glucoraphanin/TH or グルコラファニン/TA

※グルコラファニンは、素人（私）が少し調べたところ、スルフォラファンの前駆体とのことで、検索に加えてもよいのではという気がしましたが、いかがでしょうか。また、加える場合、スルフォラファンの類義語として含めてよいものでしょうか。恐れ入りますが、依頼者に照会の必要があるようでしたらお手数をおかけします。

（日本語検索では結果件数に影響しませんが、他のDBの参考に、念のため確認できればと思います。）

#11 に追加で、“or SGS/TA or アブラナ科/TH”を足していただくと、#13, #14 が不要になります。

（#13, #14 について、思考プロセスを追えず恐れ入ります。若干付け加え的な感じがしたので、本体の掛け合わせに含められないか検討しました。以下に例示しますが、当初ご提案のうち1件が漏れます。ご検討お願いできますでしょうか。）

(((((Sulphoraphane/TH or "sulforaphane glucosinolate"/TA or スルフォラファングルコシノレート/TA or "Sulphoraphane"/TA or "Sulforaphan"/TA or スルフォラファン/TA or スルフォラフェン/TA or "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane"/TA or "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate"/TA or "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or "Methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"/TA or SFN/TA or 実生/MTH or Glucoraphanin/TH or グルコラファニン/TA) and ("Glucosinolates"/TH or "Isothiocyanates"/TH or

"Glucosinolates"/TA or グルコシノレート/TA or グルコシノラート/TA or "Isothiocyanates"/TA or イソチオシアネート/TA or イソチアシアン酸類/TA or イソチオシアナート/TA or SGS/TA or アブラナ科/TH)) not ((CK=動物) not (CK=ヒト))) and (PT=会議録除く)) 94件 2023/8/15 現在

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Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

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Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

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This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

MEDLINE

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

PubMed

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健康成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** 健康成人
- I** SGSを含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? **[mandatory]**

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```
*** sulforaphane ***
1      "sulforaphane" [Supplementary Concept] 1,730
2      "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane"[Title/Abstract:~0] OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate"[Title/Abstract] OR
"4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"[Title/Abstract:~0] OR sulforafan[Title/Abstract] OR "sulforaphane"[tiab] 2,790
3      #1 OR #2 2,880
*** glucoraphanin とかけあわせ ***
4      "glucoraphanin" [tw] 424
5      #3 AND #4 255
*** ブロccoliーとかけあわせ ***
6      "broccoli seed extract"[tiab] OR "broccoli seed extracts"[tiab:~0] OR "broccoli sprout"[tiab] OR "broccoli sprouts"[tiab]
328
7      #6 AND #3 218
8      9548634[tw] 3 //PubChem CID
9      ("SFN"[tiab] AND "SGS"[tiab]) AND "Sulforaphane"[tw] 3
10     "sulforaphane glucosinolates"[tiab:~0] OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate"[tw] 11
11     #5 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 405
12     animals [mh] NOT humans [mh] 5,142,638
13     #11 NOT #12 335
```

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2023/08/17

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested

- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

1. Sulforaphane と glucoraphanin は類義語に近い捉え方で OR 検索ではいかがでしょうか。
2. #2 末尾の 2 つについて、意図されているのでしたら構いませんが、sulforafan はヒット 2 件程なので変更もありかと思えます。 sulforafan[Title/Abstract] OR "sulforaphane"[tiab] →例：sulphoraphan*[TW] OR sulforaphan*[TW]
3. 今回ブロッコリースプラウトに限定しないということでサブリ等も含むとすると、Sulforaphane AND (ブロッコリーOR #8 OR #9 OR #10) ですとやや限定的になるように思います。

○#6 植物で掛け合わせる場合、アブラナ科に広げてはいかがでしょうか。

例："Brassicaceae"[MeSH] OR cruciferous[tw] OR crucifera*[tw] OR "broccoli"[tw] OR "brassica"[tw]

○アブラナ科植物以外（サブリ等？）を拾う目的で、#8～#10 に加えて、Sulforaphane と掛け合わせる条件を複数設けた方が漏れ防止のためより安心かと思いましたが、いかがでしょうか。（ノイズ等を十分確認できていませんが・・・）

・ "glucosinolates"[MeSH Terms] OR "glucosinolate*"[Text Word] OR "SGS"[tiab]

・ ("isothiocyanates"[MeSH] OR "isothiocyanate*"[Text Word]) AND ("sulfoxides"[MeSH] OR "sulfoxide*"[Text Word])

理由：sulforaphane の臨床試験文献ではこの 2 つの mh がセットで含まれることが多いように思い、例示しましたが、物質名などを理解していないため、この掛け合わせが適当なのか不明です。

上記を Sulforaphane と掛け合わせると、PMID: 35010950, 28112972（今回該当するか分かりませんが）を拾います。

4. 1～3 の検索ですと 2000 件になるので、研究デザインでの絞込みが必要になりそうです。

当初の検索の 300 件は程良い件数だと思います。全体として、ノイズ等も考慮してご検討いただけたらありがたいです。

中途半端なフィードバックで恐縮です。よろしくお願いいたします。

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Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Reviews: Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library(Wiley)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健康成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** 健康成人
- I** SGSを含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? **[mandatory]**

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1	(sulforaphane NEXT glucosinolate*):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
#2	((broccoli NEXT seed NEXT extract*) OR (broccoli NEXT sprout*)):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
#3	("glucora phanin" OR glucoraphanin*):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
#4	(sulforaphane):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
#5	("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane"):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
#6	#4 OR #5 in Cochrane Reviews	0
#7	#2 AND #6 in Cochrane Reviews	0
#8	(glucoraphanin):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
#9	#6 AND #8 in Cochrane Reviews	0
#10	(SFN AND SGS):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
#11	#1 OR #7 OR #9 OR #10 in Cochrane Reviews	0

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707=10.3389/fnut.2022.1077271(DOI)=CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2023/08/17

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

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2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
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6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

検索ありがとうございます。

CENTRAL と共通の検索式で、絞込み (*in Cochrane Reviews*) を設定していただけたらと思います。ゼロ件でした。

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Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: *Click or tap here to enter text.*

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファンゲルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library(Wiley)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健康成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** 健康成人
- I** SGSを含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取

- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```
#1 (sulforaphane NEXT glucosinolate*):ti,ab,kw in Trials 9
#2 ((broccoli NEXT seed NEXT extract*) OR (broccoli NEXT sprout*)):ti,ab,kw in Trials 135
#3 ("glucora phanin" OR glucoraphanin*):ti,ab,kw in Trials 58
#4 (sulforaphane):ti,ab,kw in Trials 212
#5 ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane"):ti,ab,kw in Trials 214
#6 #4 OR #5 in Trials 214
#7 #2 AND #6 in Trials 92
#8 (glucoraphanin):ti,ab,kw in Trials 58
#9 #6 AND #8 in Trials 51
#10 (SFN AND SGS):ti,ab,kw in Trials 3
#11 #1 OR #7 OR #9 OR #10 in Trials 121
```

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707=10.3389/fnut.2022.1077271(DOI)=CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2023/08/17

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

1. Sulforaphane と glucoraphanin は類義語に近い捉え方で OR 検索ではいかがでしょうか。
2. 掛け合わせ等、全体の検索式は PubMed と共通の方針に合わせていただけたらと思います。
 - #1 glucosinolate*との掛け合わせは、近接でない通常の AND 検索も可能でしょうか。
 - #2 必要に応じて以下を足して広げる可能性が考えられます。

MeSH descriptor: [Brassicaceae] explode all trees
(cruciferous OR crucifera* OR broccoli* OR brassica*):ti,ab,kw

3. #3 が迷子と思われませんが（意図的に残している？）、#8 と重複のようなのでいずれか一つで十分でしょうか。

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

CINAHL Plus with Full Text

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

EBSCOhost

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健康成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** 健康成人
- I** SGSを含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? **[mandatory]**

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Cochrane RCT filter (CINAHL 用を一部編集して使用)

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

*** sulforaphane glucosinolate ***
S1      TX sulforaphane N0 glucosinolate*      TX sulforaphane N0 glucosinolate* Search modes - Boolean/Phrase
        18
*** sulforaphane ***
S2      TI ( ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-
methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan* OR sulforaphane* ) ) OR AB ( ( "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-
Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan* OR sulforaphane* ) ) Search modes -
Boolean/Phrase      430
S3      TX sulforaphane*      Search modes - Boolean/Phrase      846
S4      S2 OR S3 Search modes - Boolean/Phrase      847
*** glucoraphanin とかけあわせ ***
S5      TI glucoraphanin* OR AB glucoraphanin* Search modes - Boolean/Phrase      50
S6      S4 AND S5 Search modes - Boolean/Phrase      37
*** ブロccoliーとかけあわせ ***
S7      TX ((broccoli W0 seed W0 extract*) OR (broccoli W0 sprout*)) Search modes - Boolean/Phrase      215
S8      S4 AND S7 Search modes - Boolean/Phrase      127
S9      S1 OR S4 OR S8      159
S10     ((MH ANIMALS+ NOT (MH HUMAN OR MH "Male")) OR (MH (ANIMAL STUDIES) NOT MH (HUMAN)) OR (TI (ANIMAL
MODEL) NOT MH (HUMAN))) Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase      193,059
//Cochrane RCT filter を改変して一部使用
S11     S9 NOT S10      Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 141

```

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2023/08/19

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested

- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Pubmed の検索式に合わせていただけたらと思います。
 S2 "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate"
 OR sulfurafan* OR sulfuraphane* **OR sulphoraphane***
 S7 (MH "Cruciferous Vegetables+")も含めてご検討いただけたらありがたいです。

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

African Index Medicus, Index Medicus for the Eastern Mediterranean Region, Index Medicus for the South-East Asia Region, Latin America and the Caribbean Literature on Health Sciences, Western Pacific Region Index Medicus

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健常成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** 健常成人
- I** SGS を含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

1      tw:("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")      0
2      tw:("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphinylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphinylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-
methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane")      78

```


3	<i>tw:("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane")</i>	78
4	<i>tw:("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")</i>	6

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2023/08/19

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.")

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
---------	--------------	-----------------------	----------------------

1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

#2 "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin 件数増えませんが記載しておく？
#2, #3 検索式重複？

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者D

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): [mandatory]

ICTRP

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健康成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** 健康成人
- I** SGSを含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? **[mandatory]**

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

1      in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate") 0
2      in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl
Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane") 80 records for 79 trials
found!
3      in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl
Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane") 51 records for 51 trials
found!
4      in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate") 4
records for 4 trials found!
5      in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate") 71
records for 69 trials found!
6      in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR
"broccoli sprouts") 54 records for 54 trials found!

```

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2023/08/19

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested

C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

#2, #5 は、"1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane" OR glucoraphanin 1件増えます。
#3 は、"broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts"の検索ですね。

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

PROSPERO

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健康成人を対象として、SGS を含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** 健常成人
- I** SGS を含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

1      "sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate"          0
2      "1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-
methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane"          13
3      "broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts"  1

```

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2023/08/17

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

#1, 2 確認しました。ありがとうございます。

#3 broccoli* OR crucifer*も加えるのはいかがでしょうか。（広すぎる？）

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

ClinicalTrials.gov(classic)

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健康成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design** — as applicable)

- P** 健康成人
- I** SGSを含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? **[mandatory]**

- Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1	Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")	26
2	Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane") AND glucoraphanin	23
3	Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")	65
4	Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("sulforaphane glucosinolates" OR "sulforaphane glucosinolate")	20
5	Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("1-isothiocyanato-4-methylsulphanylbutane" OR "4-Methylsulphanylbutyl Glucosinolate" OR "4-methylsulfoxybutylisothiocyanate" OR sulforafan OR "sulforaphane") AND glucoraphanin	18
6	Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("broccoli seed extract" OR "broccoli seed extracts" OR "broccoli sprout" OR "broccoli sprouts")	59

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707, CN-02550556(CENTRAL)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2023/08/19

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

#2, #5 末尾の箇所、OR glucoraphanin としてはいかがでしょうか。
#3, #6 brassica 等に広げるとノイズが多く増えるため、ご提案通りでよいかと思います。

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date submitted: 2023/08/05

Date requested by: *Click or tap here to enter text.*

Search Topic or Title:

SGS (スルフォラファングルコシノレート) による肝機能の維持・改善作用

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

UMIN-CTR

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

健常成人を対象として、SGSを含む食品の経口摂取が、同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取と比較して、肝機能を維持・改善するか

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** 健常成人
- I** SGSを含む食品の経口摂取
- C** 同物質を含まないプラセボ食品の経口摂取
- O** 肝機能を維持・改善
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

1      フリーワード検索：検索キーワード スルフォラファン グルコシノレート 2
2      フリーワード検索：検索キーワード sulforaphane glucosinolate      1
3      フリーワード検索：検索キーワード Sulphoraphane 0
4      フリーワード検索：スルフォラファン      17 //8/5
5      フリーワード検索：スルフォラフェン      0
6      フリーワード検索：ブロッコリスプラウト      2
7      フリーワード検索：BS 抽出物 0
8      検索：目的1 スルフォラファン グルコシノレート 1
9      検索：目的1 sulforaphane glucosinolate      1
10     検索：目的1 Sulphoraphane      0
11     検索：目的1 スルフォラファン      12
12     検索：目的1 スルフォラフェン      0
13     検索：目的1 ブロッコリスプラウト      1
14     検索：目的1 BS 抽出物      0
//計 37(重複除去後 18)

```

Key articles: 2018321874, 36618707

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: 非開示

Date completed: 2023/08/18

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

トータル 19 件?